

Just A Timely Passing Butterfly

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First Sight

A small butterfly
Fluttering on a flower
My gaze rests on it

Admiration

Bright, colorful wings
Shining in the gentle sun
A joy to my eyes

Courage

I open my hand
Hoping its gentle small wings
Will rest by my side

Nervous

That butterfly came
Flying closely to my hand
My heart trembles soft

Joy

Soft butterfly wings
Landing frailly on my hand
Warm joy fills my heart

Care

Tired lovely small wings
Rest softly upon my hand
I will guard you safe

Kilig

Small, delicate wings
Dancing, flying in the air
Warm laughter within

Silence

Suddenly, it flew
The wings are gone, gone timely
The garden grows cold

Pain

One small butterfly
Once on my hand, now it's gone
Watching from afar

Longing

The butterfly left
Yet its gentle, fragile wings
Live in memory